

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF SERVICES

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

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Abstract. *In the context of the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, the factors affecting the efficiency and quality of services provided by service enterprises are researched and proposals are made to improve the efficiency and quality of services.*

Keywords: *digital economy, automation, efficiency factors, service quality, transformation.*

Introduction. We know that there are various factors that influence the effectiveness of services. However, not all of these factors have a positive effect on service quality. Scientists argue that in the service industry, a decrease in efficiency usually leads to a decrease in quality, or vice versa.

The achieved result refers to the quality of the service provided to the client, how satisfied the client is with this service and how much this service is evaluated. Expenses are a patient wait for the return of expenses with a positive effect over time, and in case of failure, emotional and spiritual readiness for this trouble is understood.

Sales of services, profit from sales and share of services on the market, labor resources spent on providing services, and equipment and technologies used. From the client's point of view, overachievement leads to decreased self-efficacy, overvaluation and, as a result, a significant decrease in value.

Therefore, everyone knows that an improvement in one area, an increase in positive indicators, in turn, always leads to a decrease in other positive indicators in that area and a deterioration in efficiency (and) service industry managers need to improve efficiency only if they focus on other approaches, and not from the client's point of view, positive results will increase because the same approach does not always work.

Thus, efficiency and quality are independent concepts. The efficiency factor refers to the production of as much output as possible at a given cost, and the quality factor refers to the achievement of high-quality productivity as a result of the service provided to customers and customer satisfaction with those services. From the outside it seems difficult to achieve such a result, increase productivity and quality of service at the same time. Using the latest literature and news, in this article we examine factors that can simultaneously improve both efficiency and quality of service.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Factors that increase service efficiency. Although the importance of improving service efficiency is highly appreciated, due to the lack of conceptual models that capture the essence of the research field under study, changes in the field are partially covered, resulting in an insufficient scientific news database. Thus, the results of our research on the factors influencing service effectiveness and service performance indicate that these studies are conceptual rather than empirical in nature.

At the moment, several factors have been studied to improve the efficiency of the service. To understand how each of them affects the quality of service, it is necessary to familiarize yourself with each of them in detail.

1. Organizational culture factor is studied on the basis of management criteria: it focuses on how resources are allocated and managed, how employees understand what is important and truly valued by the organizations in which they work, as well as on their work and how relationships influence on clients. ' perception of service quality. Such questions can be answered by studying and analyzing the criteria of organizational culture and management. Thus, it can be said that organizational culture and management criteria influence both productivity and quality.

2. Factor of standardization of services. Through standardization, businesses can reduce costs, which increases productivity and lowers prices, which in turn leads to competitive advantage.

However, the diversity of consumer demand, the participation of a large number of “personal”-individual services and a thin set of clients, coupled with an increase in the efficiency of standardization of services, also lead to a decrease in the quality of services; services are provided to a large number of clients. For example, if we take the process of transferring knowledge to students in the field of higher education, then if a large number of students study in large classrooms, productivity increases, the lack of opportunity to work individually with students leads to a decrease in their quality indicator. or in the case of a car plant, even more so. If you manufacture a car, due to inattention to some details, this will lead to a drop in the quality indicator. Standardization and quality of service are more suitable for industries where there is little variation in supply and demand and services are repetitive, such as fast food, banking, insurance, car rental and dry cleaning.

3. Automation (computerization) is a factor of new technologies. The purpose of investing in new technologies is to improve efficiency because they help replace the need for human labor with new technologies. Automation allows employees to work faster and better, while increasing productivity. The use of technology results in improved service quality while reducing costs and damage. However, this may depend on customer segments and type of service providers. Previous research has shown that technological labor displacement is more common in industries with less direct human contact, such as banking. On the other hand, technological progress brings little benefit to the trade or hotel business. This is because it may improve efficiency but not maintain quality of service as customers see more appeal in people than in technology.

4. Factor of knowledge and professional training of service workers: human capital plays a decisive role in increasing labor productivity. This is because most services are produced by people, and therefore “the quality and effectiveness of services depends largely on people.” However, attempts to complete the job faster are often unsuccessful because they can lead to errors or unsatisfactory results, which may result in the job being re-done. Working hard with employees to simultaneously improve productivity and service quality requires a focus on employee efficiency and effectiveness. Increasing employee technical skills (efficiency) means increasing employee productivity as well as the quality of their work.

Field productivity is reduced due to lack of technical skills among employees, decreased productivity, and time spent on self-correction. Service workers' attitudes and behaviors (productivity) influence service quality and productivity, as dissatisfied customers can create additional workload and staff dealing with these complaints can reduce productivity. The results

of the study showed that an effective hotel employee can achieve higher quality of service, and also that effective employees tend to produce more services, in this regard, the knowledge and professional skills of training service personnel are important.

5. Incentive and Recognition Factor: Research has shown that motivation at work, if explained through the back-office concept, is very suitable for services with little customer contact, but on the other hand, front office is explained through the incentive concept. High levels of customer service lead to decreased productivity because service employees spend more time and effort on customers, which may improve service quality but not efficiency. Thus, recognition of incentives and recognition can improve the quality and efficiency of services in situations where human factors have less influence on customers. Because in this case, most of the employee's time is spent doing more work.

6. Employee Satisfaction Factor: As we mentioned above, we have tried to explain the concepts between employee job satisfaction and performance indicator. Employees will only work more efficiently if they are satisfied with their jobs and are loyal to their company, which in turn increases productivity. Indeed, satisfaction has a significant impact on productivity. On the other hand, when employees are dissatisfied with their jobs, they tend to be less productive.

Dissatisfaction leads to a threefold increase in employee turnover, and employee turnover leads to decreased productivity and customer satisfaction. Research shows that employee satisfaction is also linked to customer satisfaction. Satisfaction motivates employees to work harder, achieve positive results in meeting customer needs, and provide good service: the more satisfied employees are with their jobs, the better the quality of customer service. Thus, employee job satisfaction affects both productivity and quality.

7. Supply and demand coordination factor: Services are mostly produced and consumed simultaneously, which means that real-time production is important to coordinate supply and demand, such situations are especially observed in the airline and hotel service industries. For example, at the beginning of the season, demand exceeds available capacity, capacity is fully utilized, and therefore efficiency is maximized, but service quality may suffer because this situation causes customers to spend too much time queuing or customers are more likely to become frustrated with the situation. On the other hand, at the end of the season we can observe the opposite situation described above.

Therefore, demand forecasting is essential to meet available resources and maximize production capacity. With proper forecasting, demand can be balanced by using part-time staff during the season or off-season, or by outsourcing some services to other support organizations. Well-trained and qualified employees help maintain the quality of service. Therefore, the same coordination of supply and demand is necessary to simultaneously improve efficiency and quality.

Conclusions and offers. The main conclusions of the above article are that the factors that simultaneously improve efficiency and quality vary depending on the type of service industry. Therefore, in order to implement digital transformation and in connection with the growing need for quality service, to strengthen active cooperation with interested organizations and enterprises operating in the field, to develop educational standards and work training programs adopted in the service sector, as well as to carry out coordination, it is necessary to actively cooperate with specialized higher educational institutions (with scientific qualifications and experience in this field).

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